

UWB and GNSS Sensor Fusion Using ML-Based Positioning Uncertainty Estimation

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ABSTRACT This article presents a novel machine learning (ML) augmented sensor fusion scheme for seamless indoor-outdoor positioning using ultra-wideband (UWB) and global navigation satellite system (GNSS) sensors. Dilution of precision (DOP) is a common metric that describes the level of geometrical uncertainty and is often applied in sensor fusion schemes. However, it does not fully reflect other factors that may influence positioning integrity, such as signal quality, pseudorange error, or the number of servicing nodes. An incorrect estimation of sensor uncertainty may significantly affect the precision and robustness of individual sensors and their fused positioning solution, especially in indoor-outdoor transition zones, where positioning is most challenging. Therefore, this article proposes a sensor fusion scheme augmented with two distinct extreme gradient boosted (XGBoost) ML models for estimating UWB and GNSS positioning uncertainties. Trained using real-life datasets, these models have the advantage of considering an ensemble of features rather than a single parameter to estimate the uncertainty of the current coordinate. In contrast to sensor fusion solutions, which implement only highly accurate RTK fixed solution mode, the GNSS model can operate with different correction qualities as well. The proposed scheme was applied on a moving testbed with UWB and GNSS sensors while relying on the ML models to enhance the coordinate filtering. The results show that the ML-based approach can improve seamless transition between indoor and outdoor areas with almost no sensor dropouts with a mean positioning error of 0.16 m and a maximum error of approximately 0.5 m.

INDEX TERMS Coordinate uncertainty estimation and filtering, indoor and outdoor navigation, machine learning, seamless UWB and GNSS positioning, sensor fusion.

I. INTRODUCTION

USING positioning sensors to achieve an accurate and precise end coordinate of an object indoors, outdoors, or between those areas is a challenging task. The performance of these systems is highly dependent on the operational environment. For example, the global navigation satellite system (GNSS) performs well in outdoor open-sky areas with unobstructed reception from servicing satellites. On the other hand, the signal from satellites is usually severely degraded indoors or in urban areas, making GNSS positioning challenging [1], [2], [3]. Similarly, considering

an ultra-wideband (UWB) based positioning system, it is also intended to work within an area serviced by a network of UWB anchors [4]. UWB systems typically employ radio-frequency (RF) signals in a frequency range between 3.1 GHz to 10.6 GHz and a bandwidth greater than 500 MHz [5], [6]. The latter attribute makes the UWB signal more robust in the presence of multipath effects and less susceptible to interference when compared to other RF-signal-based positioning systems [4], [7], [8]. Usually established indoors, the UWB-based system provides an alternative positioning solution in GNSS-denied environments.

For a positioning solution that is capable of locating an object both indoors and outdoors with a seamless transition from one environment to another, the system would need to incorporate information from both indoor and outdoor positioning sensors. Based on numerous works presented in the literature, it can be seen that achieving a reliable transition between the two environments is still a challenge. The problem arises when moving positioning sensors from one operational environment to the other (e.g., indoors to outdoors). As the signal quality of one positioning sensor degrades, the error of the sensor coordinates increases. On the other hand, when transitioning into an area dominated by signals of the other sensor, the positioning uncertainty of this positioning system decreases with an increase in signal quality. While seamless indoor-outdoor positioning accuracy and precision may be enhanced by implementing additional sensors (e.g., inertial measurement unit (IMU) or wheel sensor), the end coordinate still depends on the integrity of each individual positioning sensor. Therefore, the current article seeks to enhance the seamless coordinate accuracy and precision using only information from UWB and GNSS sensors.

In a seamless positioning system, one of the main challenges is to determine the uncertainty of the end coordinate in the transition zone. While both indoor and outdoor sensors are operating at the edge of their operational area, it is still necessary to estimate their uncertainty. An appropriate integrity parameter in a coordinate filtering scheme (e.g., Kalman filter (KF)) may significantly improve seamless transition from one operational area to the next. Coordinate solutions from different sensors would be given weights based on their positioning integrity, thereby increasing bias toward the solution with less uncertainty.

In the literature, there are different approaches to determining this uncertainty. For example, Zhang et al., proposed to use the circular error probable (CEP) metric for the indoor UWB network, while positioning error from global positioning system (GPS) was described as the difference between current GPS measurement and the estimate of the integrated magnetic, angular rate, and gravity (MARG)/GPS solution [9]. They reported an average positioning accuracy of approximately 3 m. As CEP is primarily used to evaluate the precision of stationary points, it would be difficult to use this metric for a moving object. Furthermore, as pointed out by Lv, Wang, Jin, and Shen, this method needs to know the prior error distribution of the UWB system in the deployment area. Additionally, the positioning systems are switched based on values presented by GNSS horizontal dilution of precision (HDOP) and UWB CEP threshold, which may not guarantee smooth and stable trajectories in the transition area [10]. The literature shows that dilution of precision (DOP) is often used as a parameter in determining the uncertainty of positioning. Using the estimated position, the DOP value indirectly shows the level of geometrical uncertainty in an area relative to servicing nodes (e.g., GNSS satellites or UWB anchors) [11]. Considering a coordinate

filtering scheme with two sensors, the one with a larger DOP value would be treated as more imprecise compared to another sensor [12]. Lv et al. proposed to use HDOP in their seamless positioning solution that consisted of GNSS real-time kinematics (RTK), UWB, IMU and wheel sensor [10]. They achieved 8 cm static positioning accuracy and a stable transition between indoor and outdoor areas. Yao et al. used HDOP for UWB and carrier-to-noise ratio for GNSS as weights in a tightly coupled GNSS/UWB/inertial navigation system (INS) positioning scheme with federal filtering, achieving approximately 10 cm horizontal accuracy in the transition area [13]. Zhu et al. developed an integrated positioning strategy using GNSS, UWB, dead reckoning (DR), and visual map matching (VMM) with HDOP-based uncertainty weights for GNSS and UWB, achieving approximately 0.8 m overall horizontal accuracy [14].

However, it can be argued that DOP alone does not provide enough information about positioning uncertainty. For example, the accuracy of the GNSS positioning depends on three types of errors. Firstly, there are receiver instrument errors, which may influence the performance of positioning precision. Next, there are errors caused by the signal propagation path. These include ionospheric and tropospheric delays as well as multipath effects. Finally, there are errors caused by the space segment, including satellite ephemeris, clock drift and position errors related to the geometry of constellations. Only the receiver's position relative to orbiting satellites can be observed through dilution of precision values [15], [16]. It can be seen that DOP describes only a small part of the entire ensemble of error sources. Therefore, sensor fusion solutions, incorporating only a single parameter of error (e.g., HDOP), may lack sufficient data to fully describe positioning errors. Moreover, the data interface of the GNSS receiver may output many other parameters such as the number of servicing satellites, age of correction, deviation of position error, correction quality, etc., which may also be considered.

The sources of error for UWB positioning systems may be analyzed similarly. Although not as susceptible to propagation path effects, the UWB positioning quality is affected but not limited by factors such as the number of servicing anchors, their vicinity to the tag, impairments caused by non-line of sight (NLOS), and suitable anchor layout geometry [7], [11], [17].

Geofencing is another method that could be used to switch between indoor and outdoor positioning systems. For example, Wang et al. proposed a tightly coupled GNSS/UWB/INS/Map integration scheme for autonomous vehicles [18]. Indoors, the system compares object position relative to the map and makes observations of UWB signal occlusions (blockage between the UWB anchors and the tag) to reduce NLOS errors, thereby improving seamless transition between indoor and outdoor areas. Di Pietra, Dabove and Piras suggested to use geofencing as a trigger to switch positioning sensors between indoor and outdoor areas in a pedestrian navigation scheme with GNSS, UWB,

and INS sensors [19]. While geofencing has advantages in discarding erroneous indoor or outdoor positioning data, it can be argued that several disadvantages exist. Firstly, while in a transition area, the end coordinates of an indoor or outdoor positioning sensor might be cut off too soon, as reception of these sensors usually extends a significant distance into their adjacent operational area. Secondly, geofencing cannot describe uncertainty of the positioning coordinate. Lastly, this method requires prior knowledge of the operational area, usually in the form of a predefined map or track making the solution area-specific and cumbersome to implement.

In contrast to the aforementioned methods, this paper presents an alternative approach in estimating the positioning uncertainty using machine learning (ML). One of the main advantages of ML-based approaches is the ability to make decisions effectively using observed data without explicit mathematical formulation [20]. Compared to traditional statistical methods, ML techniques enable the identification of complex dependencies in data that may not be apparent through exploratory data analysis. The main contributions of this paper are as follows:

- This article proposes a machine learning (ML) augmented complementary sensor fusion solution for GNSS and UWB positioning systems. The extreme gradient boosted (XGBoost) models incorporate a combination of features that could provide a more comprehensive estimation of coordinate uncertainty compared to single parameter solutions. These features include ones used in the literature as well as parameters that, to the best of author's knowledge, have not been applied before. For example, when DOP is a parameter commonly used as a sole indicator of positioning uncertainty, then in this article it is just one of many features used in both the GNSS and UWB ML models. The models' output provides an estimate of the sensor's true coordinate offset and is used as measurement uncertainty within the coordinate filtering process.
- The GNSS ML model has been trained using data with different correction qualities: differential GPS (DGPS), floating-point RTK, and RTK fix. Such an approach contrasts with other works that only consider highly accurate RTK fix data or propose tightly-coupled fusion where the RTK floating-point ambiguities are solved within a dedicated algorithm [10], [21], [22], [23].
- The GNSS and UWB ML models were trained on data collected in real-life industrial and commercial buildings. For unbiased results, the obtained models were tested in a separate environment. Therefore, it may be suggested that this solution does not require prior knowledge of the deployment area.

The solution in this article can be considered as semi-loosely coupled GNSS and UWB fusion. UWB coordinates and features are extracted from raw UWB ranging information making it a tightly coupled part of the solution.

On the other hand, GNSS sensor features and coordinates are extracted from the readily available National Marine Electronics Association (NMEA) messages with no need for feature and coordinate calculations. Therefore, the GNSS sensor is loosely coupled, in contrast to tightly coupled solutions, which rely on extracting pseudorange data from the GNSS receiver. Moreover, the ML augmented sensor fusion could be potentially used with off-the-shelf RTK devices, provided that these output appropriate features for the ML model.

The UWB ML model was trained based on data gathered at three different indoor environments, which contained a UWB anchor network. The GNSS ML model was trained based on data collected at a single location, which included outdoor, near-building, and indoor areas. Both models were trained and tested using the XGBoost ML library [24]. The two models were then used to estimate the offset from the true coordinate for the respective positioning sensor. These estimates along with GNSS and UWB coordinates were then combined using measurement fusion. Finally, the fused values were then applied in a coordinate filtering scheme of an Adaptive Kalman Filter (AKF). In essence, the merit of using a ML model is to incorporate more than one feature to enhance the estimation of uncertainty of the respective sensor, thereby improving end coordinate accuracy and precision in a multi-sensor positioning solution.

The paper is organized as follows: Section II describes end coordinate estimation for UWB and GNSS localization as well as features used in both models. Section III gives an overview of data collection, ML model training, validation, and testing. Section IV describes the application of the ML uncertainty estimate in sensor fusion and coordinate filtering. Section V describes testing equipment, area, and test results. The article is concluded in Section VI.

II. COORDINATE ESTIMATION AND FEATURES

This article proposes a UWB and GNSS sensor fusion algorithm that employs ML-based positioning uncertainty estimations. As stated in the introduction, accurate coordinate uncertainty estimation has a central role in achieving an accurate fused coordinate, especially in situations where the integrity of one or several sensors is compromised. The general flowchart is shown in Fig. 1 and comprises of multiple steps. The GNSS outputs geodetic coordinates as well as GNSS RTK-specific features for the ML model. The global coordinates are transformed into a local frame of reference using the East-North-Up (ENU) method.

On the other hand, the UWB sensor outputs only ranging information, which is used to calculate UWB tag coordinates using multilateration with a non-linear least squares (NLS) approach. The features of the UWB ML model are calculated based on the NLS solution and initial ranging information. As each ML model produces a separate estimate for uncertainty, these estimates are merged with covariance fusion techniques. Local coordinates would be fused and weighted based on ML predictions. Lastly, fusion output is

FIGURE 1. Flowchart of UWB and GNSS ML augmented sensor fusion. The dashed box represents the author's contribution in developing two distinct ML models for respective sensor uncertainty estimation. Sensor coordinates and their dynamically changing position uncertainties are fused and filtered to produce the end coordinate at the output.

FIGURE 2. Example of a 2D trilateration scheme with inaccurate range measurements. The difference between the distance to the estimated position \hat{d}_i and the actual measured range d_i results in a residual Δd_i that can be used in estimating positioning uncertainty [27].

filtered with an adaptive Kalman filter (AKF) to produce the final coordinate estimate.

A. UWB LOCAL COORDINATE CALCULATION

Estimating the position of the UWB tag, regarding surrounding anchors, represents a problem of multilateration. Fig. 2 shows an object on coordinates (\hat{x}, \hat{y}) in the vicinity of three anchors denoted with (x_i, y_i) . Distance measurements d_i from each individual anchor can then be used to estimate the tag's position. Usually, to obtain a solution in 2D space, at least three-, and in 3D space four anchors are required [25]. Additionally, the geometry of the anchor layout may influence positioning results. For example, anchors positioned in a straight line may produce flip ambiguity with possible solutions on either side of the line [26]. Without any measurement errors, $d_i = \hat{d}_i$ and the least squares (LS) method provides a solution at the intersection of the three circles [28]. However, real-life positioning is usually impacted by ranging noise and NLOS, thereby requiring the application of optimization techniques [8], [29]. In this

article, the 3D end coordinate of the tag is first estimated with LS and then further optimized with a non-linear least squares (NLS) approach by minimizing the objective function:

$$\hat{x}, \hat{y}, \hat{z} = \underset{x, y, z}{\operatorname{argmin}} \sum_{i=1}^N \left((x_i - x)^2 + (y_i - y)^2 + (z_i - z)^2 - d_i^2 \right)^2 \quad (1)$$

where x , y and z are the coordinates that provide the smallest error. Detailed LS and NLS calculation steps are explained in different works by authors such as Guvenc and Guillory [25], [30].

The difference between a measured distance d_i from the respective anchor, and distance \hat{d}_i from the estimated coordinate $(\hat{x}, \hat{y}, \hat{z})$, is represented as a ranging residual Δd_i as:

$$\Delta d_i = d_i - \hat{d}_i. \quad (2)$$

In this work, it is suggested that ranging residuals and their statistical values are used in the UWB ML model to indirectly describe UWB positioning integrity.

B. FEATURES OF UWB ML MODEL

The UWB ML model estimates coordinate uncertainty based on statistics of ranging residuals, coordinate optimization techniques, and geometrical integrity. The ensemble of features used by the model is following: LS/NLS difference, sum of squares of ranging residuals, sum of squares of positive ranging residuals, residual variance, number of NLS iterations, position DOP (PDOP), mean of residuals, and variance of positive residuals. Feature calculation equations are given in the author's article about ML-based UWB positioning integrity estimation [27].

C. GNSS LOCAL COORDINATE CALCULATION

East-North-Up transformation is a method of projecting geodetic coordinates onto a local flat tangent plane. For example, the geodetic coordinates extracted from the GNSS receiver can be transformed onto Cartesian plane, which is more intuitive, and allows to make distance calculation using Euclidean geometry. This projection is practical for establishing a unified indoor-outdoor reference frame in small areas. To define the projection, it is needed to specify the point of tangency (origin). That location becomes the center of projection and is usually the center of the project site [31].

The transformation is twofold. Firstly, the geodetic latitude ϕ , longitude λ , and height h values are converted into Earth-centered, Earth-fixed (ECEF) coordinate system [32]:

$$N(\phi) = \frac{a^2}{\sqrt{a^2 \cos^2 \phi + b^2 \sin^2 \phi}}, \quad (3)$$

$$X = (N(\phi) + h) \cos \phi \cos \lambda, \quad (4)$$

$$Y = (N(\phi) + h) \cos \phi \sin \lambda, \quad (5)$$

$$Z = \left(\frac{b^2}{a^2} N(\phi) + h \right) \sin \phi, \quad (6)$$

TABLE 1. Features from NMEA messages [33].

Message	Field	Description	Symbol	Example
\$GPGGA	7	GPS quality indicator	x	4
\$GPGGA	8	Number of satellites in use	xx	11
\$GPGGA	9	Horizontal dilution of precision	x.x	1.1
\$GPGGA	14	Age of correction data (in seconds)	xx	8
\$GPGST	3	RMS value of the standard deviation of the pseudorange measurements	x.x	2.7
\$GPGST	7	Standard deviation of latitude error (m)	x.x	1.2
\$GPGST	8	Standard deviation of longitude error (m)	x.x	3.2
\$GPGST	9	Standard deviation of altitude error (m)	x.x	4.5

where a and b are Earth’s equatorial and polar radii respectively and X, Y, Z represent ECEF coordinates. This transformation would be done using geodetic coordinates of both the point of interest (e.g., GNSS rover) and point of origin (e.g., GNSS base station), denoted by X_p, Y_p, Z_p and X_o, Y_o, Z_o respectively. Next, these values are shifted with regards to the point of origin. The vector values (E, N and U) from the origin to the point of interest are calculated as:

$$\mathbf{R}_r = \begin{bmatrix} -\sin \lambda_o & \cos \lambda_o & 0 \\ -\sin \phi_o \cos \lambda_o & \sin \phi_o \sin \lambda_o & \cos \phi_o \\ \cos \phi_o \cos \lambda_o & \cos \phi_o \sin \lambda_o & \sin \phi_o \end{bmatrix}, \quad (7)$$

$$\mathbf{R}_s = \begin{bmatrix} X_p - X_o \\ Y_p - Y_o \\ Z_p - Z_o \end{bmatrix}, \quad (8)$$

$$\mathbf{R}_r \times \mathbf{R}_s = \begin{bmatrix} E \\ N \\ U \end{bmatrix}, \quad (9)$$

where \mathbf{R}_r and \mathbf{R}_s mark the rotation and shifting matrices respectively. ENU coordinates for the point of origin are $(0, 0, 0)$ and the length between the origin and point of interest can be calculated with the Euclidean distance formula. ENU method satisfies the need to map the coordinates in a small area on the Earth as it conforms so nearly to a plane that distortion on such a system is negligible [31].

D. GNSS FEATURES

The GNSS receiver used in this research outputs data with the following NMEA 0183 message headers: $\$GPGGA$, $\$GPGST$, $\$GPZDA$, $\$GPRMC$ and $\$GPVTG$. Table 1 presents the fields considered as most relevant in describing positioning quality and therefore applied in GNSS ML model training. As mentioned in the introduction, the GNSS features can be extracted from the serial interface of the receiver and require no additional calculations. The GNSS device used in this research operates with three correction

states, which indicator can be extracted at $\$GPGGA$ field 7. These corrections include DGPS (value 2), floating-point RTK (value 5) and fixed RTK (value 4).

DGPS is an extension of GPS technology, based on satellite and terrestrial communication. A station with a known location is considered as a source of reference, which communicates additional data to the receiver to reduce localization error. The idea lies in determining errors related to pseudorange observables and is calculated by comparing the value from the GNSS receiver and the value computed using the coordinates of the satellites and the reference station [34]. In urban areas, the DGPS method may provide a positioning accuracy lower than 10 m [16].

GNSS RTK is a precise positioning method capable of delivering cm-level accuracy. By leveraging simultaneous carrier-phase measurements from both the GNSS base station and the receiver, it implements differencing techniques to eliminate signal phase biases, clock offsets as well as tropospheric and ionospheric errors. A key challenge in RTK is resolving the integer ambiguity, which represents the exact number of wavelengths between a satellite and the receiver. Before the ambiguities are resolved, the GNSS receiver uses floating-point estimates for the ambiguity. Once a valid integer solution is determined, the receiver transitions to RTK fixed ambiguity solution mode, resulting in a significantly improved positioning accuracy [35], [36].

The $\$GPGST$ log contains pseudorange measurement noise statistics that are translated into the position domain to give statistical measures of the quality of the position solution. This log reflects the accuracy of the solution type used in the $\$GPGGA$ message, except for the RMS field, which does not represent carrier-phase-based positions but the accuracy of the pseudorange position [33].

III. DATA COLLECTION, ML MODEL TRAINING AND TESTING

A. UWB MEASUREMENT DATA COLLECTION, PROCESSING AND MODEL TRAINING

The UWB ML model was trained on data collected at two different sites which contained an indoor UWB network: OÜ Krah Pipes factory and OÜ Eliko Tehnoloogia Arenduskeskus office. Based on the Qorvo’s DW1000 chip, the Eliko real-time locating system (RTLs) was set to operate on UWB channel 4 [37]. It also uses active-passive two-way ranging (AP-TWR) protocol with clock offset error mitigation [38]. The goal was to collect UWB ranging data at different locations, calculate UWB model features, and assign separately measured ground truth offset as the ML model’s response variable. The ground truth was measured in a local frame of reference with the Leica DISTO S910 laser distance measurement tool, which assigned 3D coordinates to UWB anchors as well as the tag. The measurement tool has a typical accuracy of ± 1 mm [39].

The model was tested in a separate area at Auroom Kastre factory (Fig. 3), which contained a network of 15

FIGURE 3. Industrial site at Auroom Kastre factory. Five of a total of 15 UWB anchors are highlighted with red circles.

FIGURE 4. Layout of the GNSS measurement campaign at the Eliko office building. Static measurements were taken indoors, near-building, and in outdoor areas. For clarity, only 15 measurement points out of a total 60 measurements are shown in the figure. The blue and orange traces mark the highly inaccurate and imprecise DGPS and RTK float solutions taken indoors. Measurements that were taken closer to the building door, were also more accurate and precise, while points with RTK fix solution had the best precision and accuracy.

UWB anchors. Ranging and ground truth data were collected at 40 different points around the factory. Detailed maps of UWB measurement campaigns and ML model training steps can be seen in the author’s publication concerning UWB coordinate corrections with ML techniques [27]. In the current article, the XGBoost ML model was used to estimate the uncertainty of UWB positioning using features mentioned in Section II-B.

B. GNSS MEASUREMENT DATA COLLECTION

GNSS measurement data were collected with the Fieldbee L2 RTK receiver at an office building site, as seen in Fig. 4 [40]. Before measurement collection, the RTK base

FIGURE 5. Histograms for all three GNSS correction qualities taken during the measurement campaign.

FIGURE 6. GNSS data processing flowchart.

station was set up near the test site and assigned with pre-measured geodetic coordinates. Ground truth coordinates were measured in a local frame of reference with the Leica DISTO S910 measurement tool, which had line-of-sight (LOS) with all the measurement points. The goal was to take static measurements in different environments: in obstructed, semi-obstructed, and open-sky areas. In summary, GNSS measurement data were recorded for 30 seconds at 60 different measurement points with a 10 Hz update rate. Data distribution regarding the three correction qualities is shown as histograms in Fig. 5. As expected, when GNSS RTK solves the integer ambiguities (mentioned in Section II-D), it has the best accuracy compared to other correction methods. The floating-point RTK had the largest accuracy range from approximately 1 m to 15 m. During the measurements, it was seen that indoors, at the furthest distance from the door, the main correction method was DGPS, which produced coordinates with varying offsets ranging from approximately 2 m to 25 m.

C. GNSS DATA PROCESSING AND ML MODEL TRAINING

GNSS data were processed similarly to UWB measurements and the general flowchart can be seen in Fig. 6. Collected data were extracted based on features shown in Table 1.

Also, using measurements from the Leica DISTO S910 tool, the coordinate offset was calculated and added as a response variable to the GNSS features. The purpose of the ML model was to estimate end-coordinate error based on corresponding data from GNSS features. To ensure unbiased training data, the measurements and respective response variables were sampled and divided into three equal-sized subsets, corresponding to the three correction methods: DGPS, RTK floating-point, and RTK fix. Lastly, the selected dataset was mixed and divided into segments for training and testing with a partition of 80 and 20 percent respectively.

XGBoost was the chosen ML library for model training and testing due to its proven effectiveness in previous UWB positioning applications. Its ability to deliver both accurate and computationally efficient estimations is essential for high-update-rate positioning systems [27], [41]. The algorithm employs a sequential approach, constructing a series of gradient-boosted trees. Each subsequent tree is trained to correct the errors of its predecessor, and the final prediction is a summation of all individual tree predictions. Furthermore, in recent years XGBoost has become a popular decision tree-based ensemble ML technique that has been dominating applied ML for structured or tabular data and has been successfully used for regression or classification by researchers since its release [42]. Supervised XGBoost learning was done in the RStudio environment using imported *xgboost* library [24], [43].

After data partitioning, 80 percent of the data was used for 10-fold cross-validation to select suitable hyperparameter values for the initial model. RStudio provides appropriate cross-validation *train*, *xgbTree* and *trainControl* functions with the *caret* library [44]. The training dataset, which consisted of collected features and their response variables, was separated into 10 segments with 1 segment being the validation set. This approach helps to choose more generalized hyperparameter values [45]. The main hyperparameters for XGBoost were tree depth and number of boosting iterations [46]. Using cross-validation with the *xgboost* library, different XGBoost hyperparameter values were compared in terms of prediction root mean square error (RMSE) as shown in Fig. 7. Hyperparameter values were limited, which can help avoid overfitting and an overly complex model [47]. Also, it can be seen that a model with a tree depth of 7 and 100 boosting iterations is sufficiently accurate, as choosing more than 100 iterations would present no significant increase in prediction performance.

The hyperparameters, training dataset, and response variables were then used to build the initial model with the *xgboost* function from the ML library. It should be noted that no prior feature selection was done before model cross-validation. Alternatively, XGBoost library in RStudio contains a built-in function *xgb.importance* to output features that provide the biggest informational gain in making the prediction. After establishing an initial model, inherent features were ranked in descending order of their informational

FIGURE 7. Prediction RMSE varies with different hyperparameter values. Tree depth and the number of boosting iterations were limited to 7 and 100 respectively as these values provide sufficient prediction accuracy and help avoid overfitting and an overly complex model.

FIGURE 8. The prediction RMSE as a function of the number of features. Using more than 5 features has no significant impact on prediction accuracy and may lead to overfitting of the model.

gain. Next, by selecting a sequential combination of features, prediction RMSE was observed to select the number of features that provide a sufficiently accurate estimation. As shown in Fig. 8, more than 5 features provide no significant increase in predicting test set response values. In contrast, choosing more features may lead to overfitting and an overly complex model [48]. The final selected features and their informational gain are shown in Fig. 9.

D. GNSS ML MODEL TESTING

The final GNSS ML model was tested on a dataset, which was not used in the training process as shown in Fig. 6. Because of data mixing, the test set also contained samples with different correction qualities. As can be seen in Fig. 10, the ML model predicts coordinate offset with high accuracy. The performance was evaluated with common regression metrics: RMSE, mean square error (MSE), and

FIGURE 9. 5 features that provide the biggest informational gain in the XGBoost model. The gain quantifies how much a feature contributes in improving the models prediction.

FIGURE 10. Prediction error of GNSS ML model for different correction qualities. The vertical axis is presented in the logarithmic scale.

FIGURE 11. Sample density comparison of ML prediction and test set values for different correction qualities.

mean absolute error (MAE). Sample distributions of the test set and corresponding predictions can also be seen in Fig. 11.

IV. COORDINATE FUSION AND FILTERING

A. COORDINATE AND COVARIANCE FUSION

Measurement fusion is one of the most common data fusion methods in a system with complementary sensors [49]. Considering the positioning sensors used in this article, measurement fusion is done for UWB and GNSS coordinates and their covariances or uncertainty measures. Firstly, using the predicted estimate \hat{y}_U of the UWB model and \hat{y}_G from the GNSS ML model, their respective covariance matrices are established as:

$$\mathbf{R}_U = \begin{bmatrix} \hat{y}_U^2 & 0 \\ 0 & \hat{y}_U^2 \end{bmatrix}, \quad (10)$$

$$\mathbf{R}_G = \begin{bmatrix} \hat{y}_G^2 & 0 \\ 0 & \hat{y}_G^2 \end{bmatrix}. \quad (11)$$

Next, assuming measurements with normally distributed probability density functions (PDF) a joint PDF \mathbf{R}_F is calculated as:

$$\mathbf{R}_F = \left(\mathbf{R}_G^{-1} + \mathbf{R}_U^{-1} \right)^{-1}. \quad (12)$$

Lastly, estimated coordinates $\hat{\mathbf{Z}}_U$ from UWB and $\hat{\mathbf{Z}}_G$ from GNSS, their respective covariances, and fused covariance are used to produce fused coordinates as:

$$\hat{\mathbf{Z}}_k = \mathbf{R}_F \left(\mathbf{R}_G^{-1} \hat{\mathbf{Z}}_G + \mathbf{R}_U^{-1} \hat{\mathbf{Z}}_U \right). \quad (13)$$

B. ADAPTIVE COORDINATE FILTERING

In this work, an adaptive Kalman filter (AKF) is used to filter end coordinate estimates with fused covariances. Considering that UWB and GNSS positioning is done in different operational environments, with dynamically changing obstructions and multipath effects for both sensors, it is required to estimate the positioning uncertainty at each coordinate update. Furthermore, GNSS positioning uncertainty is dependent on the correction quality, which also changes dynamically as was shown in Fig. 4. In essence, the ML predictions for both sensors drive the filtering process by dynamically changing measurement uncertainty, i.e., whether to trust measurement or process. In the current filtering scheme, the state transition matrix \mathbf{A} for position, velocity, and acceleration was established as:

$$\mathbf{A} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & \Delta t & \frac{\Delta t^2}{2} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & \Delta t & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & \Delta t & \frac{\Delta t^2}{2} \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & \Delta t \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}, \quad (14)$$

where Δt is measurement period of 0.1 s. And process noise matrix \mathbf{Q} as:

Algorithm 1 Adaptive Kalman Filter

Input: $\hat{\mathbf{X}}_0, \hat{\mathbf{Z}}_k, \mathbf{P}_0, \mathbf{Q}, \mathbf{R}_{F_k}$
Output: $\hat{\mathbf{X}}_k$
Initialize $\mathbf{A}, \mathbf{P}_0, \mathbf{H}, \mathbf{I}$
Prediction step
for $k = 1, \dots, \infty$
1: State prediction $\hat{\mathbf{X}}_k^- = \mathbf{A}\hat{\mathbf{X}}_{k-1}$
2: Covariance prediction $\mathbf{P}_k^- = \mathbf{A}\mathbf{P}_{k-1}\mathbf{A}^T + \mathbf{Q}$
Correction step
3: Kalman gain $\mathbf{K}_k = \mathbf{P}_k^- \mathbf{H}_k^T (\mathbf{H}_k \mathbf{P}_k^- \mathbf{H}_k^T + \mathbf{R}_{F_k})^{-1}$
4: State correction $\hat{\mathbf{X}}_k = \hat{\mathbf{X}}_k^- + \mathbf{K}_k (\hat{\mathbf{Z}}_k - \mathbf{H}_k \hat{\mathbf{X}}_k^-)$
5: Covariance correction $\mathbf{P}_k = \mathbf{P}_k^- (\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{K}_k \mathbf{H}_k)$
return $\hat{\mathbf{X}}_k, \mathbf{P}_k$
end for

$$\mathbf{Q} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\Delta t^4}{4} & \frac{\Delta t^3}{2} & \frac{\Delta t^2}{2} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ \frac{\Delta t^3}{2} & \Delta t^2 & \Delta t & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ \frac{\Delta t^2}{2} & \Delta t & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \frac{\Delta t^4}{4} & \frac{\Delta t^3}{2} & \frac{\Delta t^2}{2} \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \frac{\Delta t^3}{2} & \Delta t^2 & \Delta t \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \frac{\Delta t^2}{2} & \Delta t & 1 \end{bmatrix} \sigma_a^2, \quad (15)$$

where σ_a is random acceleration standard deviation with a heuristically chosen value of 10^{-4} m/s^2 . As the filtering is done only for the x and y coordinates, the observation matrix is set up as:

$$\mathbf{H} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}. \quad (16)$$

The order of steps inside the AKF are shown in Alg. 1. The initialization coordinates $\hat{\mathbf{X}}_0$ are extracted from the sensor, which has the lower uncertainty estimate based on the respective ML model. \mathbf{P}_0 represents the initial state covariance, which was set as $\mathbf{I} \cdot 100$, with \mathbf{I} being a 6-by-6 identity matrix.

V. RESULTS

A. TEST SETUP

Tests were conducted at Tallinn University of Technology using an indoor garage with a 6-anchor UWB Eliko RTLS system. In the outdoor area a Fieldbee L2 GNSS RTK base station and a Trimble S6 total station were installed using pre-measured reference points [40], [50]. Geodetic coordinates were transformed into the local frame of reference using the ENU method as explained in Section II-C, with GNSS RTK base station at local coordinates (0, 0). The UWB tag, GNSS receiver, and reflection prism of the total station were fixed to a trolley, which also included a computer for collecting the positioning data as seen in Fig. 12. The aim was to move the test trolley from indoors to the outdoor area and return indoors while simultaneously collecting positioning data from GNSS receiver, UWB, and total station devices.

The initial total station setup was established using the resection method with three reference points [51]. These were acquired using a Trimble R12 GNSS receiver in RTK

FIGURE 12. Test setup at the campus area of Tallinn University of Technology.

TABLE 2. Positioning systems used in the test.

	Eliko RTLS UWB	Fieldbee L2 GNSS RTK	Trimble S6
Accuracy	0.2 m	0.01 m + 1 ppm CEP (RTK fix)	4 mm + 2 ppm and 2'' angular
Sample rate	10 Hz	10 Hz	2.5 Hz
Method	AP-TWR	Real-time kinematic	LOS with reflection prism
Coordinate system	Local	Global	Global

mode with three initializations (60 epochs per measurement). After establishing the initial base station, the three reference points were remeasured using the total station for consistent coordinates, and the reference network was further densified. The improved network formed the basis for further validation measurements. By comparing the initial Trimble R12 and total station measurements, an approximate absolute accuracy of 10 mm could be assumed for validation surveys.

As can be seen in Table 2, the total station has a sample rate of 2.5 Hz. In order to calculate correct performance metrics, sample rates of all systems must match at 10 Hz. Therefore, extra markers were added to the total station points through interpolation. Additionally, the UWB tag and GNSS receiver were positioned with an offset regarding the reflection prism. Therefore, their output coordinates were rotated and shifted to match the location of the prism. Since IMU data was not used during the test, the direction of the trolley was calculated in post-processing using interpolated points of the total station. During the test, the collected data on the two computers were included with a Unix timestamp, and the system clocks were synchronized against a time-server at *nettime.pool.ntp.org*.

B. INTERPRETATION OF RESULTS

An example of a test track can be seen in Fig. 13. Indoors there is poor GNSS satellite reception and only DGPS

FIGURE 13. Coordinates from GNSS and UWB sensors taken along the indoor-outdoor-indoor movement path with arrows showing the movement direction. Traversing from the building, DGPS and RTK-float solutions are highly inaccurate, presenting a coordinate offset approximately 60 m from the starting point. Returning indoors, GNSS receiver fluctuates between different coordinate correction modes, while retaining a stable trajectory.

FIGURE 14. GNSS and UWB sensor fusion using HDOP-based uncertainty with AKF for benchmarking with all available GNSS corrections (DGPS, RTK float, and RTK fix).

corrections are used. This results in highly inaccurate GNSS solutions up to 60 m away. As the trolley moves out of the garage, the receiver changes into RTK floating-point mode and receives RTK fix in a few meters from the building. When the trolley approaches the building, the GNSS fluctuates between RTK fix and float modes as the satellite reception degrades. However, GNSS maintains an acceptable heading also with RTK float, which does not deviate much from the heading with the RTK fix. This test shows that RTK float, while inaccurate indoors, may contribute accurate positioning information when returning from the RTK fix state. UWB positioning worked as expected, providing accurate coordinates indoors, with small dispersion. However, the positioning quality deteriorated rapidly when moving away from the anchors.

Measurement fusion was done only with GNSS and UWB coordinates using two different methods for estimating uncertainty. The idea was to compare ML-based and HDOP-based estimation. As stated in the introduction, dilution of precision is a common measure of uncertainty. However, as it reflects only the level of geometrical uncertainty, this article proposed to use a ML model with an ensemble of features to establish a better estimate for uncertainty. By using data gathered from the test track in Fig. 13,

FIGURE 15. GNSS RTK and UWB sensor fusion using HDOP-based uncertainty estimation with AKF for benchmarking with RTK fix only.

GNSS and UWB measurements were fused and filtered with two different approaches for measurement uncertainties. Fig. 15 illustrates measurement fusion with HDOP-based uncertainties using UWB and GNSS with RTK fix, similar to works by Lv, Yao and Zhu [10], [13], [14]. HDOP parameter was extracted from GNSS \$GPGGA field 14 and UWB HDOP was calculated using pseudoranges, anchor positions

FIGURE 16. The proposed GNSS and UWB sensor fusion with ML-based uncertainty estimation with AKF using all available corrections.

and tag's estimated position. At each measurement, the \mathbf{R}_F matrix in the AKF is updated with HDOP values to give less weight to measurements with bigger geometrical uncertainty. As shown in Fig. 15 this approach has disadvantages. Firstly, as only GNSS with RTK fix is used, this fusion leads to sensor dropouts as seen near the garage door. The track has gaps when there is no UWB solution and no GNSS RTK fix. Positioning is restored when the RTK fix is achieved or when there is a UWB coordinate available. Furthermore, when all GNSS correction modes are incorporated in the fusion scheme, then HDOP does not produce a valid uncertainty estimate for RTK float and DGPS modes. As shown in Fig. 5 and Fig. 14, the coordinate offset may vary significantly, and the DOP parameter may produce a false estimate for the uncertainty. Moreover, as weighting is performed for both GNSS and UWB coordinates, it can be seen how stable indoor UWB coordinates in Fig. 13 cannot mitigate fused coordinate error due to highly inaccurate GNSS coordinates and its uncertainty estimation in Fig. 14.

On the other hand, ML-based uncertainty estimation can be applied with all GNSS corrections as the model is trained in different correction modes and conditions similar to the test area as was shown in Fig. 4. As DGPS and RTK float present solutions in a wide range, the ML model considers this information when making the uncertainty estimation. For example, at the beginning of the test, the ML model assigns a significant offset to DGPS and RTK float as the features in the model reflect information of a highly inaccurate GNSS solution. However, these points are still considered in the coordinate filtering process and are not discarded. Also, when returning from the RTK fix state, the ML model assigns lower weights to the uncertainty as it considers a more accurate RTK float solution. The result of using the ML augmented sensor fusion scheme is illustrated in Fig. 16.

C. PERFORMANCE EVALUATION

Table 3 shows overall sensor fusion results with different approaches. Following metrics were used to evaluate positioning accuracy and precision: mean location error (MLE),

TABLE 3. Comparison of different sensor fusion schemes.

	MLE [m]	RMSE [m]	Maximum error [m]
Proposed ML-based fusion with all corrections	0.16	0.18	0.49
Fusion with RTK fix and HDOP	0.14	0.19	1.29
Fusion with all corrections and HDOP	4.56	9.64	35.32

RMSE, and maximum error [52], [53]:

$$MLE = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \sqrt{(x_T - \hat{x}_i)^2 + (y_T - \hat{y}_i)^2}, \quad (17)$$

$$RMSE = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n [(x_T - \hat{x}_i)^2 + (y_T - \hat{y}_i)^2]}, \quad (18)$$

$$MAX = \max_{i \in n} \left(\sqrt{(x_T - \hat{x}_i)^2 + (y_T - \hat{y}_i)^2} \right). \quad (19)$$

where (x_T, y_T) are the ground truth coordinates and (\hat{x}_i, \hat{y}_i) mark the estimated fusion coordinates. In Table 3 it can be seen how the HDOP-based approach with RTK fix has an MLE and RMSE at a similar level to ML-based estimation. However, the former method suffers from sensor dropouts in the transition area, resulting in a significant maximum error. Additionally, using HDOP with all available corrections (DGPS, RTK float, and RTK fix), results in an incorrect uncertainty estimation leading to a highly inaccurate fused coordinate.

VI. CONCLUSION

This article investigated how ML-based positioning uncertainty estimation can be used to improve indoor and outdoor positioning with sensor fusion. A key challenge for any similar solution is to estimate the uncertainty of each positioning system (GNSS or UWB) which contributes positioning data with a certain degree of integrity. While many sensor fusion solutions employ a single uncertainty parameter (e.g., DOP), this article considers a combination of features in a ML model, which helps to improve the overall uncertainty estimation. Also, this article considers the use of GNSS correction data with different degrees of quality - RTK fix, RTK floating-point, and DGPS. While these modes produce coordinates with varying accuracy and precision, this data can still be used with ML-based uncertainty estimates. By leveraging different features from GNSS NMEA messages, it was shown that the ML model can identify accurate or inaccurate GNSS corrections and apply estimated weights in a coordinate filtering scheme of an AKF. The results show that ML-based filtering outperforms the DOP-based approach. Overall, ML-based fusion had an MLE of 0.16 m, RMSE of 0.18 m, and maximum error of 0.49 m. Whereas, the DOP-based approach with RTK fix had respective values of 0.14 m, 0.19 m, and 1.29 m.

When DOP is used with all available corrections, these values are significantly higher, as DOP produces inaccurate uncertainty estimates for the GNSS in indoor and transition areas. In essence, DOP-based uncertainty estimation is not a comprehensive parameter since it only describes geometrical uncertainty. Furthermore, when applying DOP with UWB and RTK fixed mode only, there are large positioning gaps in the transition area caused by missing positioning data. On the other hand, the proposed ML model was trained in all available correction modes and different operational areas: indoors, transition areas, and outdoors. This approach makes UWB and GNSS sensor fusion with ML-based uncertainty estimation more stable and may further be improved with additional training data and complementary sensors (e.g., IMU, wheel sensor).

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